

WORK ETHICS OF EMPLOYEES OF SELECTED PRIVATE SECTOR COMMERCIAL BANKS IN NAGAPATTINAM DISTRICT

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Abstract

Efficient management of human resource of a bank and work ethics of employees will lead a banking company to great success, hence the researcher has made an attempt to study selected aspects of work ethics of selected private sector banks in Nagapattinam district of Tamilnadu state. The present study has been undertaken with primary data collected from 150 sample respondents through questionnaire. The researcher selected three private sector banks namely ICICI Bank, Axis Bank, HDFC Bank in the study area and collected data from 50 respondents each from each bank. The researcher applied percentage, mean and ranking method as statistical tools for analyzing the data. The researcher analysed 11 aspects of work ethics of employees in private sector banks in Nagapattinam districts of Tamilnadu state. It is found from the study that optimum work load is present in private banks, no monotonous job, since different types of works are allotted to employees, they accept that there is high responsibility and accountability in private banking job. On the other hands, the respondents are felt that working hours are not convenient and they felt that there is high work than what they expected.

Key Words: Ethics, private banks, accountability and privatization.

Introduction

Finance industry is one of the key industries in services sector in Indian economy. Financial system of the country is the backbone for all economic activities which

helps for the development of a country. Strong financial system will lead an economy for fast development. Financial institutions channelize savings of the people towards industrial development of a country. Finance is the life blood of any business, trade, commerce and industry. Now-a-days, banking sector acts as the backbone of modern business by providing financial facilities and other financial supports. Development of any country mainly depends upon the banking system. Banking industry is the key industry in service sector. Hence strong financial system is essential for the development of an economy. Banks are primary components of financial system of the country. Banks channelize capital from the savers to industry, it leads to industrial development of the country and it helps for economic development of the country. Initially Accepting deposits and lending loans are the primary functions of a bank. But over the period of time banks started to provide various financial services to its customers. Banks are also rendering secondary functions such as, overdraft facility, discounting bills of exchange and agency functions namely, transfer of funds, collection and payments, purchase and sale of foreign exchanges, purchase and sale of securities, income tax consultancy, trustee and executor and letter of reference. Apart from the above functions commercial banks also provide, locker facility, letter of credit, underwriting securities, Automatic Teller Machine (ATM), online transfer of funds and so on. Commercial banks are defined by Culbertson as “Commercial banks are the institutions that make short make short term bans to business and in the process create money”. Generally banks are classified as public sector banks and private sector banks, private sector banks are further classified as old private sector banks, new private sector banks and foreign banks.

Statement of the Problem

In present scenario, there is severe competition in any business type. Especially in banking industry the level of competition is severe between public sector and private sector banks. Once banking industry was in the hands of the government and in early 90s the Government of India brought major changes in its economic policies and allowed privates into banking business, since then many private sector banks

have come into the business and make competition in the industry tough through introducing innovative banking services and introducing technologies. Primary objective of a private bank is to earn profit, a bank can maximize its profit only through efficient management. Primary capital of banking business is human resource. Efficient management of human resource and work ethics of employees will lead a banking company to great success, hence the researcher has made an attempt to study selected aspects of work ethics of selected private sector banks in Nagapattinam district of Tamilnadu state.

Objectives

The study has been undertaken with the following objectives.

- To study demographical profile of the respondents and
- To study work ethics of selected private sector banks in the study area.

Methodology

The present study has been undertaken with primary data collected from 150 sample respondents through well structured questionnaire in Nagapattinam district in the state of Tamilnadu. The researcher selected three private sector banks namely ICICI Bank, Axis Bank, HDFC Bank in the study area and collected data from 50 respondents each from each bank using convenient sampling method. The researcher applied percentage, mean and ranking method as statistical tools for analyzing the data.

Results and Interpretation

This part of the paper presents the results and interpretation. Table 1 presents the results of demographical background of the respondents in the study area.

Table 1: Demographical Profile of the Respondents

Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Age		
Up to 25 years	18	12.0
26-40 years	74	49.3
41-55 years	36	24.0

Above 55 years	22	14.7
Gender		
Male	112	74.7
Female	38	25.3
Educational Qualification		
Technical	29	19.3
Post Graduate	59	39.3
Under graduate	45	30.0
Below under Graduate	17	11.4
Experience		
Up to 5 years	24	16.0
6 to 10 years	81	54.0
11 to 15 years	17	11.3
More than 15 years	28	18.7
Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 1 shows that age of 49.3 per cent of the respondents is between 26 and 40 years, age of 24 per cent of the respondents is between 41 and 55 years, age of 14.7 per cent of the respondents is above 55 years and age of 12 per cent of the respondents is below 25 years. It is also noted that 74.7 per cent of the respondents are male and 25.3 per cent of the respondents are female. The results of educational qualification wise classification of the respondents show that 39.3 per cent of the respondents had an educational qualification at post graduate level, 30 per cent of the respondents completed upto graduation level, educational qualification of 19.3 per cent of the respondents is technical education and 11.4 per cent of the respondents had an educational qualification of below under graduation level. It is also noted from the table that experience in banking industry of 54 per cent of the respondents is from 6 to 10 years, experience of 18.7 per cent of the respondents is above 15 years, experience of 16 per cent of the respondents is less than 5 years and

experience of 11.3 per cent of the respondents is between 11 and 15 years. It is observed from the above results that age of about half of the respondents is between 26 and 40 years, majority of the respondents are male, a considerable portion of the respondents completed upto post graduation level of education and majority of the respondents had an experience of 6 to 10 years in banking industry.

Table 2 presents the results of work ethics of the sample respondents in the study area.

Table 2: Work Ethics in Private Sector Banks

Sl. No.	Particulars	SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Total
1	Work load is optimum	18 (12.0)	37 (24.7)	29 (19.3)	48 (32.0)	18 (12.0)	150 (100)
2	Bureaucratic system of work	8 (5.3)	39 (26.0)	21 (14.0)	52 (34.7)	30 (20.0)	150 (100)
3	Monotonous job	11 (7.3)	30 (20.0)	14 (9.3)	69 (46.0)	26 (17.3)	150 (100)
4	Convenient working hours	15 (10.0)	26 (17.3)	25 (16.7)	66 (44.0)	18 (12.0)	150 ()
5	Achievement of target on time	16 (10.7)	44 (29.3)	32 (21.3)	35 (23.3)	23 (15.3)	150 (100)
6	High responsibility and accountability in the work	21 (14.0)	52 (34.7)	25 (16.7)	36 (24.0)	16 (10.7)	150 (100)
7	Less work compare to what I expected	5 (3.0)	21 (14.0)	19 (12.7)	86 (57.3)	19 (12.7)	150 (100)
8	Able to manage the time schedule	16 (10.7)	43 (28.7)	34 (22.7)	41 (27.3)	16 (10.7)	150 (100)
9	Shortcoming of the work is frustrating	9 (6.0)	27 (18.0)	36 (24.0)	71 (47.3)	7 (4.7)	150 (100)

10	Happy with the location of the office	13 (8.7)	82 (54.7)	19 (12.7)	27 (18.0)	9 (6.0)	150 (100)
11	Enough time to be effective in my role	17 (11.3)	58 (38.7)	35 (23.3)	28 (18.7)	12 (8.0)	150 (100)

Source: Primary Data

It could be known from table 2 that a considerable portion of the respondents (44 per cent) either disagreed or strongly disagreed that the work load in their bank is optimum. Majority of the respondents (54.7 per cent) either disagreed or strongly disagreed that there is bureaucratic system of work in private banks. Similarly, majority of the respondents (63.3 per cent) either disagreed or strongly disagreed that there is monotonous job in private banks. In other words different types of works are allotted in private banks. Majority of the respondents (56 per cent) either disagreed or strongly disagreed that there is convenient working hours in private banks. About equally number of respondents each agreed and disagreed that they achieved the target in time. About half of the respondents (48.7 per cent) either agreed or strongly agreed that there is high responsibility and accountability in works in private banks. Majority of the respondents (70 per cent) did not agree that there is less work in private banks than they expected. A considerable portion of the respondents (39.4 per cent) could manage time schedule in private bank jobs. Majority of the respondents (52 per cent) did not agree that there are shortcoming of the work is frustrating. Majority of the respondents (63.4 per cent) are happy with location of the office and half of the respondents agreed that there is enough time to be effective to discharge their role in private banks.

Table 3 presents the results of rank of all the selected aspects of work ethics based on mean score.

Table 3: Rank of Work Ethics Aspects in Private Sector Banks

Sl. No.	Particulars	Mean Score	Rank
1	Work load is optimum	2.9	5
2	Bureaucratic system of work	2.6	7
3	Monotonous job	2.5	8
4	Convenient working hours	2.7	6
5	Achievement of target on time	3.0	4
6	High responsibility and accountability in the work	3.2	3
7	Less work compare to what I expected	2.4	9
8	Able to manage the time schedule	3.0	4
9	Shortcoming of the work is frustrating	2.7	6
10	Happy with the location of the office	3.4	1
11	Enough time to be effective in my role	3.3	2

Source: Primary Data

It is known from table 3 that the aspect of location of bank is ranked first among 11 aspects of work ethics. Majority of branches of private banks are located in heart of the city or town, hence the respondents are happy with location of office. Followed by, availability of enough time is ranked 2nd, since private bank employees can get enough time to discharge their role.

The aspect high responsibility and accountability is ranked 3rd, hence there is high responsibility and accountability in private bank jobs. The aspect of less work than what they expected is ranked last, it shows that there is high work in private banking job than what they expected.

Conclusion

Private Banks are giving tough competition to public sector banks. They try to give efficient services to their customers through well trained and efficient human resources. Efficient work style of the employees will give success to the bank, hence

work ethics is very important in private sector banks. The researcher analysed 11 aspects of work ethics of employees in private sector banks in Nagapattinam districts of Tamilnadu state. It is found from the study that optimum work load is present in private banks, no monotonous job, since different types of works are allotted to employees, they accept that there is high responsibility and accountability in private banking job. On the other hands, the respondents are felt that working hours are not convenient and they felt that there is high work than what they expected.